

EFFECTIVENESS OF HYBRID FRP STRENGTHENING ON THE SHEAR BEHAVIOUR OF REINFORCED CONCRETE BEAMS

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ABSTRACT

Reinforced concrete (RC) beams are often strengthened to improve their shear performance. The strengthening of shear deficit RC beams using fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) materials is very effective compared to conventional strengthening techniques. In this study, three near full-scale RC beams of size 300 x 300 x 1500 mm are cast and tested. They are tested under three categories (i) Control RC Beam, (ii) RC Beam strengthened the entire length using external bonding of U-Wrap with CFRP fabric (U-Wrap), (iii) RC Beams strengthened with a hybrid combination consisting of NSM laminates at regular intervals with full-length U-wrapping (Hybrid). Anchorages are provided on both faces of the beam specimen to prevent the delamination of the U-wrap. The shear performance of the U-wrap FRP strengthened RC beam significantly increased compared to the control RC beam. The hybrid system improves the shear strength and ductility than the U-Wrap system as the NSM laminates act as the additional transverse ties. Also, the efficiency of NSM strips in the hybrid FRP system increases due to limiting the micro-buckling and debonding of NSM laminates from the confinement of a full U-Wrap.

KEYWORDS

RC Beam; CFRP U-Wrap; NSM laminates; Hybrid U-Wrap and Shear Loading.

INTRODUCTION

The reinforced concrete (RC) beam elements in the existing civil infrastructures are often required to improve the shear strength due to different causes like (i) variation in the loading requirements, (ii) upgrading of design standards, (iii) ageing and deterioration, (iv) change in the safety requirements, (v) damage caused by impact loads (Garden & Hollaway, 1998; Rao & Prakash, 2022; Triantafillou, 1998). The fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) strengthening is a prominent solution for enhancing the shear performance compared to conventional steel jacketing and concrete enlargement. The FRP strengthening has numerous advantages (i) less weight/strength ratio, (ii) corrosive resistance, (iii) easy installation, (iv) requiring less space and time, and (v) higher durability (Chellapandian et al., 2017; Malleswara Rao & Prakash, 2021). The FRP strengthening can be used in different forms like near-surface mounting (NSM) of pultruded laminates (Khorramian & Sadeghian, 2019) and external prestressing with fabric and laminates (Kotynia et al., 2011), and external bonding (EB) with FRP fabric and pultruded laminates. The different forms of FRP strengthening are used to enhance the strength and stiffness of various concrete elements, such as flexure strengthening for slabs and beams (Huang et al., 2019; Rao et al., 2023), shear strengthening for beams (Guadagnini et al., 2006; Kuntal et al., 2017) and confinement on the column members (Balla et al., 2023; Mirmiran et al., 2002).

The failure mode of diagonal shear crack is formed in the RC element subjected to shear loading, which is a very brittle and sudden failure. The brittle failure needs to be prevented by strengthening the shear deficit members. Many researchers in the past investigated the shear-strengthened RC beams using FRP fabrics (Pellegrino & Modena, 2006; Triantafillou, 1998), shear links (Guadagnini et al., 2006), and FRP laminates (Ibrahim et al., 2020; Kuntal et al., 2017). Dias and Barros (2017) experimentally investigated the effectiveness of NSM strengthening in RC T-beams. The inclined laminates are observed to be more efficient than vertical NSM laminates in improving the shear capacity. Rizzo and

De Lorenzis (2009) experimentally investigated the effect of round FRP bars and FRP strips in NSM strengthening to improve the shear capacity. There is no significant effect of reducing the spacing of the NSM strips observed, as debonding failure is dominant in both cases. Bousselham and Chaallal (2006) experimentally observed the significant enhancement in shear strength of the slender RC beams with U wrap. However, no significant enhancement in shear capacity is observed in the deep beam specimens. The observations from the existing research studies, it is evident that the failure mode of FRP strengthened shear beams are FRP debonding, whether the beams are EB or NSM strengthened. Therefore, the FRP fabric's de-bonding failure leads to ineffective utilisation of the materials (Chen & Teng, 2003). Zhou et al. (2019) proposed the hybrid bonded CFRP system using mechanical fasteners to prevent the de-bonding effect. The results of many experiments have shown that using suitable anchoring mechanisms can prevent the bond separation of FRP shear-strengthened RC beams. Hybrid shear strengthening has been an effective solution in reducing the de-bonding and improving the shear performance.

The proposed innovative hybrid shear strengthening (Hybrid) combines U-wrap with CFRP fabric, CFRP anchors for arresting the debonding failure, and NSM strengthening with CFRP laminates. In this paper, the efficiency of the hybrid shear strengthening is experimentally investigated using three near full-scale RC beam specimens of 300 x 300 x 1500 mm. The hybrid technique enhances the shear performance more than the existing U wrap and NSM laminate strengthening techniques.

RESEARCH SIGNIFICANCE

The existing research investigations have been mainly focused on the shear-strengthened RC beams using the FRP fabric and FRP laminates (Kuntal et al., 2017; Rizzo & De Lorenzis, 2009; Triantafillou, 1998). The RC beams strengthened with hybrid systems can effectively enhance the shear strength and ductility by preventing the sudden brittle failure mode (Ebead & Saeed, 2013; Zhou et al., 2019). However, a thorough review of the past investigations shows that very nominal studies have focused on the hybrid FRP shear strengthening. FRP debonding is a crucial issue in FRP strengthening because it leads to the ineffective use of the material properties. To address these debonding failures, some of the researchers addressed the anchoring technique (Zhou et al., 2019). However, the research in assessing the efficiency of anchoring is very limited and has not been studied much in shear behaviour. Therefore, the proposed experimental study helps in understanding the shear behaviour of hybrid strengthened RC beams anchored with the CFRP anchors, which helps in arresting the debonding of CFRP material. Also, the outcomes of the experimental investigation are beneficial to creating the database for understanding the efficiency of the hybrid system in enhancing the shear strength and ductility of RC beams.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

Three near full-scale RC beams of size 300 x 300 x 1500 mm are cast, strengthened and tested. Eight 12 mm diameter bars are used in all the beams as longitudinal reinforcement. The 8 mm diameter at 300 mm C/C spacing in the test zone and 150 mm C/C in the remaining span are used as transverse reinforcement, as shown in Figure 1. Details of the control and FRP strengthening configurations of the test matrix are shown in Table 1. Out of three, one is the reference specimen without any strengthening (Control RC), one is strengthened on three sides with external bonding of 400 GSM CFRP fabric (U Wrap); another is strengthened using a hybrid combination using two NSM laminates of 50 x 1.75 at 200 mm C/C and U Wrap using 400 GSM CFRP fabric (Hybrid). The ends of the U wrap in both the FRP strengthened specimens are anchored with CFRP anchors to prevent the premature bond separation of the FRP fabric.

The details of the control RC and FRP strengthened specimens are illustrated in Figure 1. Details of CFRP anchor used in this study is illustrated in Figure 2. According to IS 10262 (BIS, 2009), the concrete mix design with a target concrete cube strength of 25 MPa was designed. The average cylinder compressive strength of three samples at 28 days is observed to be 28.4 MPa. Fe 550 grade steel is used for both longitudinal and transverse reinforcement. The tensile strength of CFRP laminates and hand layup CFRP fabric is observed to be 2800 and 985 MPa, respectively. The elastic modulus and tensile properties of the steel, CFRP fabric and laminates are presented in Table 2.

Figure 1: Details of control RC and FRP strengthened specimens

Figure 2: Details of CFRP anchor

Table 1: Details of the test program

Specimen Name	Control RC	U wrap	Hybrid
Size of Specimen	300 x 300 x 1500 mm		
Longitudinal Reinforcement	8 numbers of 12 mm dia.		
Transverse Reinforcement	8 mm dia. @ 300 mm c/c in the test zone and 150mm c/c in the remaining span		
Strengthening Configuration Details	RC beam without any strengthening for reference	Two layers of 400 GSM U wrap: CFRP fabric throughout the span and anchored at both side faces of the RC beam using CFRP anchor	Two CFRP laminate (each 50 mm wide) @ 200 mm c/c of as NSM at both sides of the beam + 2 layers of 400 GSM U wrap using CFRP fabric throughout the span and anchored at both sides faces of RCC beam using CFRP anchors

Test Setup

The control RC and FRP strengthened specimens are tested under three-point bending with the a/d ratio of 2.0. The test setup and instrumentation details used for testing are illustrated in Figure 3. The specimens were tested using a 1000 kN hydraulic actuator of MTS systems. The strain gauges are bonded to the steel reinforcement during the reinforcement cage preparation for monitoring the strain values during the testing of RC beams. The linear variable differential transformers (LVDT) are connected to the beam specimen for monitoring the deformations. The data acquisition system (DAQ) continuously monitors the displacements and strains from the LVDTs and strain gauges.

Figure 3: Test setup and instrumentation details

Table 2: Properties of steel reinforcement and FRP materials

Material	Modulus of elasticity (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
Steel Reinforcement	200	500
CFRP Fabric 400 GSM	99.8	985
CFRP laminate 50 x 1.75 mm	165	2800

TEST RESULTS

The comparison of load-deflection curves of the control RC beam, U wrap, and Hybrid strengthened specimens are illustrated in Figure 4. Table 3 shows the shear capacity comparison of the control and FRP strengthened beams. The deflection values illustrated in 4 are measured under the loading point. The FRP strengthened specimens effectively enhanced the shear capacity and ductility. The U-wrap and hybrid FRP strengthened specimens improved the shear strength by 94.6% and 97.6% more than the control RC beam. However, a hybrid U wrap improves strength and ductility more than the U wrap system, as the NSM laminates act as additional transverse ties. Also, the efficiency of NSM laminates in the hybrid system increased due to limiting the micro-buckling and de-bonding of NSM laminates due to confinement from the U Wrap.

Table 3: Comparison of test results

Specimen Name	Control RC	U Wrap	Hybrid
Peak Axial Load (kN)	205	398.8	404.9
Shear Capacity (kN)	102.5	199.4	202.5
% Increase	-	95	98

Figure 4: Load-deflection curves of control and FRP strengthened specimen

Strain Energy

The effectiveness of the strengthened systems can also be understood by measuring the post-peak behaviour response of strain energy. The area under the load-deflection curve up to the ultimate point is the strain energy. In this present paper, the ultimate point for measuring the energy observation is considered up to 30% load reduction of the peak load. The observed strain energy and flexibility in the conventional specimen are comparatively less than all other strengthened specimens. Table 4 shows the strain energy and percentage increase of the strain energy when compared to the control RC beam. The increase in the strain energy of hybrid strengthened specimens is found to be 275% more than the control specimen and 40% more than the U wrap strengthened specimen.

- Hybrid FRP strengthening is found to be highly effective in enhancing both shear strength and post-peak behaviour.

REFERENCES

- Balla, T. M. R., Prakash, S. S., & Rajagopal, A. (2023). Role of size on the compression behaviour of hybrid FRP strengthened square RC columns – Experimental and finite element studies. *Composite Structures*, 303(July 2022), 116314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2022.116314>
- BIS. (2009). IS: 10262 - 2009 Indian Standard Guidelines for concrete mix design proportioning. In *Bureau of Indian Standards, New Delhi*.
- Bousselham, A., & Chaallal, O. (2006). Effect of transverse steel and shear span on the performance of RC beams strengthened in shear with CFRP. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 37(1), 37–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2005.05.012>
- Chellapandian, M., Prakash, S. S., & Sharma, A. (2017). Strength and ductility of innovative hybrid NSM reinforced and FRP confined short RC columns under axial compression. *Composite Structures*, 176(July), 205–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2017.05.033>
- Chen, J. F., & Teng, J. G. (2003). Shear capacity of FRP-strengthened RC beams: FRP debonding. *Construction and Building Materials*, 17(1), 27–41. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0950-0618\(02\)00091-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0950-0618(02)00091-0)
- Dias, S. J. E., & Barros, J. A. O. (2017). NSM shear strengthening technique with CFRP laminates applied in high T cross section RC beams. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 114, 256–267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2017.01.028>
- Ebead, U., & Saeed, H. (2013). Hybrid shear strengthening system for reinforced concrete beams: An experimental study. *Engineering Structures*, 49, 421–433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2012.11.039>
- Garden, H. N., & Hollaway, L. C. (1998). An experimental study of the failure modes of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with prestressed carbon composite plates. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 29(4), 411–424. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-8368\(97\)00043-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-8368(97)00043-7)
- Guadagnini, M., Pilakoutas, K., & Waldron, P. (2006). Shear Resistance of FRP RC Beams: Experimental Study. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 10(6), 464–473. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)1090-0268\(2006\)10:6\(464\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)1090-0268(2006)10:6(464))
- Huang, X., Sui, L., Xing, F., Zhou, Y., & Wu, Y. (2019). Reliability assessment for flexural FRP-Strengthened reinforced concrete beams based on Importance Sampling. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 156, 378–398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2018.09.002>
- Ibrahim, M., Wakjira, T., & Ebead, U. (2020). Shear strengthening of reinforced concrete deep beams using near-surface mounted hybrid carbon/glass fibre reinforced polymer strips. *Engineering Structures*, 210(October 2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2020.110412>
- Khorramian, K., & Sadeghian, P. (2019). Performance of high-modulus near-surface-mounted FRP laminates for strengthening of concrete columns. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 164, 90–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2018.11.064>
- Kotynia, R., Walendziak, R., Stoecklin, I., & Meier, U. (2011). RC Slabs Strengthened with Prestressed and Gradually Anchored CFRP Strips under Monotonic and Cyclic Loading. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 15(2), 168–180. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)cc.1943-5614.0000081](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)cc.1943-5614.0000081)
- Kuntal, V. S., Chellapandian, M., & Prakash, S. S. (2017). Efficient near surface mounted CFRP shear strengthening of high strength prestressed concrete beams – An experimental study. *Composite Structures*, 180, 16–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2017.07.095>
- Malleswara Rao, B. T., & Prakash, S. S. (2021). Shape Effects on the Behavior of Hybrid FRP–Strengthened Rectangular RC Columns under Axial Compression. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 25(5), 04021042. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)cc.1943-5614.0001152](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)cc.1943-5614.0001152)
- Mirmiran, A., Shahawy, M., Samaan, M., Echary, H. El, Mastrapa, J. C., & Pico, O. (2002). Effect of Column Parameters on FRP-Confined Concrete. *Journal of Composites for Construction*, 2(4), 175–185. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)1090-0268\(1998\)2:4\(175\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)1090-0268(1998)2:4(175))
- Pellegrino, C., & Modena, C. (2006). Fiber-reinforced polymer shear strengthening of reinforced concrete beams: Experimental study and analytical modeling. *ACI Structural Journal*, 103(5),

- 720–728. <https://doi.org/10.14359/16924>
- Rao, B. T. M., Morthala, R. R., & Suriya Prakash, S. (2023). *Experimental Investigation on Flexural Behaviour of RC Beams Strengthened with Various FRP Composite Configurations*. Fiber Reinforced Polymeric Materials and Sustainable Structures. Composites Science and Technology . Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-8979-7_9
- Rao, B. T. M., & Prakash, S. S. (2022). Numerical Investigation on Size and Shape Effects on Hybrid FRP Strengthened Non-Circular RC Columns under Axial Compression. In *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering: Vol. 198 LNCE*. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-88166-5_144
- Rizzo, A., & De Lorenzis, L. (2009). Behavior and capacity of RC beams strengthened in shear with NSM FRP reinforcement. *Construction and Building Materials*, 23(4), 1555–1567. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2007.08.014>
- Triantafillou, T. C. (1998). Shear strengthening of reinforced concrete beams using epoxy-bonded FRP composites. *ACI Structural Journal*, 95(2), 107–115. <https://doi.org/10.14359/531>
- Zhou, Y., Guo, M., Sui, L., Xing, F., Hu, B., Huang, Z., & Yun, Y. (2019). Shear strength components of adjustable hybrid bonded CFRP shear-strengthened RC beams. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 163(September 2018), 36–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2018.11.020>

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.